

CHEMICAL TOOLS TO CONTROL THE POTATO MOTH (*PHTHORIMAEA OPERCULELLA ZELL.*) EFFICIENCY**¹Khudoykulov Azamjon Mirzokulovich, ²Tursunov Kuvonchbek Shirkulovich**¹Associate Professor of Tashkent State Agrarian University, Ph.D.²Junior researcher of the Samarkand Regional Branch of the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Quarantine and Protection<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8372746>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the distribution, damage, bioecology of the potato moth in the potato crop, and indicators of the effectiveness of chemical agents against it. Based on the obtained results, practical proposals and recommendations for production are presented.*

Keywords: *Potato, pest, potato moth, spread, damage, chemical means, control, efficiency, phytophages, productivity.*

Enter. In the world, up to 24% of crops die annually due to pests, diseases and weeds. The total amount of damage to agriculture exceeds 75 billion dollars per year. In order to protect plants from pests, weeds and diseases, about 1000 different chemicals are currently used in different countries of the world. The use of pesticides helps to save 100,000 tons of crops per year.

At all stages of human development, providing the population with goodies is the main issue. In this case, rational protection of plants from harmful organisms (pests, diseases and weeds) is one of the main tasks. In our republic, it is important to protect cotton, grain, potatoes, fruits and vegetables and other crops and plants from harmful organisms, and to develop animal husbandry [1. pp. 3-4].

Agricultural crops are the main source of food for our people, and obtaining more of them is one of the main urgent tasks of the industry. However, harmful insects, pathogens, weeds and other harmful organisms damage agricultural crops and have a serious impact on productivity. As in all agricultural crops, a number of pests, diseases and weeds have a negative effect on the growth and development of the garden, vegetables and rice. A large part of the yield will be lost if timely measures are not taken against harmful organisms.

According to scientists and experts, if rapid and systematic measures are not developed and consistently implemented against the potato and tomato moth, which has been spreading in some regions in recent years, up to 60-80 percent of this year's crop may be damaged and die.

The potato moth is a dangerous quarantine insect that causes great damage to potatoes, tobacco, eggplant, tomatoes and other plants belonging to the family of sorghums. The butterfly is small, light gray in color. The head is dark brown or black.

A moth larva goes through 4 stages during its life, it develops for 11-26 days. Potato moth develops in 7 days when the air temperature is above +40. When the air temperature reaches +27 degrees, the development of the pest lasts 25 days. Gives 5-6 generations in a year. Under favorable conditions, the potato moth can produce up to 11-13 generations per year.

The potato moth damages both seedlings and the plants it has taken hold of, some leaves of seedlings and sometimes the entire bush are dried up. Potato moth sometimes damages the fruits of tomatoes. In addition to the leaves of the crops, the potato moth butterfly also injures the potatoes on the surface. If tubers infested with moth larvae are brought into storage after potatoes are harvested in the field, 25-80 percent of stored potato tubers may die. Most affected leaves become dry, brown, and shriveled and cracked. Moth-infested fields look burnt. In autumn,

adjacent leaves at the tips of plants often stick to each other with cobwebs. The surface of the infected potato becomes a pink spot a few days after the worm enters. Most of the affected tomato and potato crops rot [7.].

Picture 1. Potato moth butterfly. (Samarkand scientific and experimental station of ITI Samarkand. 2022)

Based on the above, studies were conducted in the potato field in order to determine the use and biological effectiveness of the drugs recommended against the potato moth.

Research methods. The researches were carried out in the 2.5-hectare potato field belonging to the scientific-experimental station of ITI Samarkand. First, the "Santa" variety of potatoes taken for the experiment was isolated, planted and cared for. The number of moths in the potato crop was calculated according to the established methodology (Sh. Khojaev 2004).

Separated drugs Emamectin benzoate 5% w.d.g. (0,5 kg/ha), Indomectin s.c. (0,2 l/ha), Lyamiksam 24,7% s.c. (0,25 l/ha) was treated with a hand sprayer at the prescribed rate of consumption.

In the experimental field, the determined days (3, 5, 7, 14) after the use of the drug were monitored based on methods. The results were as follows.

Research results. According to the obtained data, Emamectin benzoate 5% w.d.g. when we used the drug at the rate of 0,5 liters per hectare, the biological efficiency was 86,9% on the 3rd day, 95,9% on the 5th day, 92,9% on the 7th day and 89,3% on the 14th day after treatment. Indomectin s.c. 72,5% on the 3rd day, 82,9% on the 5th day, 81,4% on the 7th day and 66,5% on the 14th. Isa, Leocamicsam 24,7% s.c. In the case of 0,25 l/ha, it was 69,2% on the 3rd day, 78,6% on the 5th day, 75,0% on the 7th day, and 68,7% on the 14th day (Table-1).

Table-1

Effectiveness of chemical preparations against potato moth in potato fields.

(Vegetable crops and potatoes Scientific-experimental station of ITI Samarkand, 2022)

№	Fields of experience	Of the drug spending rate kg, l/ha	The average number of potato moths on one leaf, pcs				By efficiency % days				
			Until processing	By days after processing				3	5	7	14
				3	5	7	14				
1.	Control (Idle)	-	2,5	2,6	2,8	3,2	3,2	-	-	-	-

2.	Emamectin benzoate 5% w.d.g.	0,5	2,2	0,3	0,1	0,2	0,3	86,9	95,9	92,9	89,3
3.	Indomectin s.c.	0,2	2,1	0,6	0,4	0,5	0,9	72,5	82,9	81,4	66,5
4.	Lyamiksam 24,7% s.c.	0,25	2,5	0,8	0,6	0,8	1,0	69,2	78,6	75,0	68,7

Conclusions. Based on the results of the experiment, it can be concluded that Emamectin benzoate 5% s.c. is effective against potato moth in potato fields. If we apply the preparations containing 0.5 liters per hectare on time and in good quality, the biological efficiency will be high.

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